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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

DA market	Day Ahead market
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DIML	District Information Management Layer
DR	Demand-Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
Dx.y	Deliverable x.y
EV	Electric Vehicle
HEDNO	Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator
HENEX S.A.	Hellenic Energy Exchange S.A.
ID market	Intraday market
IPTO-ADMIE	Independent Power Transmission Operator
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LEC	Local Energy Community
LNG	Liquified Natural Gas
Mxy	Month xy
P2P	Peer to Peer
PV	Photovoltaic
RAE	Regulatory Authority for Energy
RES	Renewable Energy Storage
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable focuses on the Demonstration activities which should be deployed in the Greek pilot site in order to assess the implementation of the ACCEPT solution. This is the first version of the Demonstration activities report presenting how the objectives of the community are aligned with the Use Cases of the ACCEPT project. A detailed timeframe regarding the beginning of this implementation of these Use Case is provided along with the local regulatory barriers in Greece. The regulatory framework explains why some Use Cases can only be simulated in Greece and not realistically be implemented and affect the electricity bills of the participants. More details on how each Use Case will be deployed is provided, commenting on the technical tools that need to be developed until the trials can start. Finally, this deliverable indicates the supportive activities that have been set-up in order to maintain the smooth operation of the Demonstration Activities. Further information of the activities and the first results coming from their implementation will be described in the next versions of this report.

Introduction

1.1. Objectives and Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable details the work conducted under the Task 7.3 of the ACCEPT project. The goal of this deliverable is to describe the demonstration activities which will be deployed in the Greek pilot site, analysing how they are aligned with the objectives of the Greek community. A detailed timeframe for the start point of the Use Cases to be tested in the Greek pilot site is provided along with some comments about the technical features that need to be developed. Then, the local regulatory framework is analysed displaying all the arising problems for the implementation of the Demand-Response schemes in Greece. This deliverable also focuses on the preparation of the test-bed and the support activities which are crucial for the continuous data acquisition from the pilot sites.

The scope of the first version of the report is to describe all the actions performed from M20 until M26. Several details in the procurement, installation, and commissioning of the equipment (described in D6.7) as well as in the development of the C-App have delayed the initiation of the Demonstration activities. More details and results from these activities will follow in the second version of the report in M33.

1.2. Structure of the Deliverable

The structure of this deliverable is as follows:

- **Section 1:** Provides the main scope and objectives of the first version of the deliverable, presents the structure of the report, and indicates the interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables.
- **Section 2:** Analyzes the Community objectives along with the history of the settlement. The goal is to show the connection of the community objectives with the ACCEPT Use Cases. In addition, the regulatory framework and the constraints that affect locally this Community are displayed. Finally, the Demonstration Plan to be carried out for validation is described.
- **Section 3:** Describes how the different Use Cases will be implemented and the activities that have been realized in order to get proper data from the IoT equipment installed in the pilot houses. Moreover, the goal of each selected Use Case is further described.
- **Section 4:** This section explains the support activities that the pilot leader along with the end-users and the tech partner (Hypertech) should follow when a failure in the installed equipment is encountered.
- **Section 5:** the final section presents the next steps in the demonstration activities during the following seven months until the delivery of the second version of this report.
-

1.3. Interdependencies with Other Tasks and Deliverables

The main interdependencies of this Deliverable to Tasks and Deliverables of the same and other Work Packages can be summarized as:

D2.1: Use and Business Cases to be tested in each pilot site are described thoroughly in this deliverable. The responsible technical partners for each Use Case are also indicated.

D2.2: The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and the datasheet for each KPI are detailed in this Deliverable.

D2.4: The system architecture description and a further description of the Use Cases are provided in this Deliverable.

D2.8: Report on innovative business models and service/contract design.

D6.1: A more detailed description of the IoT infrastructure which is installed in the pilot sites.

D6.6: A first introduction to the deployment of the ACCEPT system in a controlled environment is given in this deliverable.

D6.7: This Deliverable provides a detailed description of the validation scenarios which will be tested in the Greek pilot site and is strongly connected to the Demonstration activity report.

T7.1: This task deals with consumer validation of service and content design.

WP8: This work package assesses the impact of the ACCEPT solution on the demonstration sites and analyses the results of the demonstration activities to elaborate the business plan and define the exploitation.

D9.10: This deliverable develops the replication roadmap and the plan for scaling-up of the solution based on the real pilot results.

2. Demonstration Plan

2.1. Community objectives

Aspra Spitia is a model settlement built by the French company Pechiney and was inhabited in 1965 (Figure 1) with the aim of accommodating the employees of the Aluminum of Greece and their families. It is the only development in Greece which can be considered a 'company town' ¹. Currently, the industrial complex in Agios Nikolaos does not only include the Aluminum facilities but also gas-fired combined-cycle facilities (power plants)². The settlement consists of 1,088 residential premises and hosts around 3,000 residents. There are many 3rd-generation residents living in Aspra Spitia, which shows how strong the bonding between the families and the company is.

Figure 1: Aspra Spitia in 1965.

¹ [ASPRASPIITIAHOUSINGDEVELOPMENT, DISTOMO, BOEOITIA | photiadis.gr](http://ASPRASPIITIAHOUSINGDEVELOPMENT.DISTOMO.BOEOITIA|photiadis.gr)

² [New IPP-II power plant at Agios Nikolaos energy complex - MYTILINEOS Website](http://NewIPP-IIpowerplantatAgiosNikolaosenergycomplex-MYTILINEOSWebsite)

Figure 2: Aspra Spitia in 2022.

The settlement is located in Boeotia, which is a 2h drive from Athens and the distance between the settlement and the industrial complex is shown in Figure 3. All the residents of the settlement, work and live together, participating into common community activities such as sport (tennis, football, hiking) and cultural (theatre, music) activities. This has created a strong community bond with a strong willingness to offer for the common good. There is a team of Facility Managers who are responsible for the wellbeing of the residents. Among others, Mytilineos is responsible for the installation and maintenance of the domestic hot water (DHW) boilers in the households. Aspra Spitia was recently (November 2022) celebrated as the first 'Smart City' in Greece³ [3]. Mytilineos has launched the MYTILINEOS Smart Cities platform, offering a variety of digital tools to the residents of Aspra Spitia with the aim of improving their living standards and making the settlement more sustainable. The platform will include services and applications such as smart water and waste management, energy management, traffic management, availability of the EV infrastructure network, capability to produce energy and control the consumption per household.

³ <https://www.mytilineos.com/news/press-releases/mytilineos-smart-cities-the-first-smart-city-in-greece-in-aspra-spitia-paralias-distomou/>

Figure 3: Location of Aspra Spitia compared to the industrial complex.

The concept of Smart Cities was presented to the citizens of Aspra Spitia in November 2022 and it was welcomed with enthusiasm. Following this event, a few of them proceeded to the purchase of electric vehicles and the installation of PV panels and domestic batteries. This shows that citizens of Aspra Spitia, unlike the average Greek consumer, have a strong tendency towards innovations and want to be up to date with new technologies. The concepts of sustainability and more efficient energy consumption within the household have already been introduced to the community which facilitated our role in the engagement process. Based on the priorities of the Aspra Spitia community, the following Use Cases have been chosen:

Table 1: Use Cases and KPIs tested on the Greek pilot site.

ID	Name	KPIs
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data	SR-01, SR02, SR-03
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation	EC-03, ER-04, ER-08
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting	ER-03, ER-04, ER-05
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation	AE-05, MR-01, MR-02
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility	EC-02, ER-01, ER-02
UC8	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes	ER-07, AE-03
UC9	Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes	ER-07, AE-01, AE-02, AE-03
UC11	Retailer day-ahead optimal pricing configuration	MR-02, EC-01, EC-02
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement	AE-01, AE-02, AE-04, AE-06, BU-01, BU-02, BU-03

The implementation of the Use Cases (UCs) started with the LEC engagement (UC14) during which the most suitable end-users were mapped. The selected households were visited and the smart equipment was installed, maintaining continuous interaction and engagement with the residents. Under the UC14, a questionnaire was selected to keep track of the users' first opinion about the installation. One of the most important UCs is the collection of Metering & Sensor Energy Data (UC1) which unlocks the following UCs. The data are collected from a central gateway which has been installed and commissioned in the residential premises and they are integrated to the BIML. Then, data from the BIML are ready for optimization of the Energy consumption (UC2), demand forecasting (UC3), demand elasticity profiling (UC4), Day-Ahead (DA) pricing (UC11) and P2P flexibility (UC7). Keeping active the engagement with the end-users has as a prerequisite the correct functionality of the C-App, in which the residents will be able to monitor their consumption and interact with their houses. The C-App is also mandatory for the implementation of the Demand Response schemes (UC8 and UC9) and can provide us with quantitative metrics about the responsiveness of the end-users to the recommended actions.

2.2. Local Regulatory Framework

In Greece, there is a single DSO, the Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator (HEDNO) and the energy market is supervised by the Regulatory Authority for Energy (RAE). According to article 7 entitled "Electricity Markets" of Law 4425/2016, the electricity transactions in the interconnected grid are realized in the DA market, Intraday (ID) market and in the Balancing Market or Electricity Financial Market. In more details, on the DA and ID Market, market participants have to submit their electricity order.

More specifically, in the Day-Ahead Market and the Intraday Market, electricity transaction orders are submitted by market participants with the obligation of physical delivery the next day (Physical Delivery Day). The operation of these Markets is conducted by the Hellenic Energy Exchange S.A. (HENEX S.A.), in collaboration with the Greek TSO, ADMIE (IPTO S.A.), in accordance with the Energy Exchange Regulations for the Day-Ahead Market and the Intraday Market (*Wholesale Market – Rae Website, n.d.*).

In Greece, there is only a single TSO, which is the Independent Power Transmission Operator (IPTO-ADMIE). The Hellenic Distribution Network Code can foresee the activation of distributed Demand-Response (DR) by the DSO by establishing 'Demand Control Contracts' with individual electricity consumers. The limitation is that these consumers should be located in congested network areas and HEDNO has the right to set limits or even interrupt the supply to their premises (Forouli et al., 2021). IPTO analytics provides information about the mix of the energy grid on a daily basis⁴. In more detail, the actual and the forecasted System Load, the Total Energy Production Mix and the Cross Border Physical Flows are available online.

The Greek retail market has been liberalized since August 2022 and has a validity period from 1/8/2022 to 31/7/2023. The retail electricity market is under state regulation during this period, in order to have under control the significant increases in electricity prices, starting from September 2021 due to Covid-19 pandemic and culminating during 2022 with the added effects of the war in Ukraine. The Greek government has been aligned with the European Commission and the national European regulators creating a basis for a non-discriminatory market access for all the energy suppliers through a series of regulations and directives. The Greek energy market is a place where suppliers can enter and compete relatively freely and on equal terms for the customers (Napolitano et al., n.d.).

When it comes to pricing, residential customers have the potential to sign contracts with lower tariffs for night consumption if their premises are equipped with a meter which can provide two indications. The Household Night Tariff is a double-billing tariff offered by HEDNO to interested parties after application, with a common granting process for all electricity suppliers. With this service different prices apply during two time zones, one in the day and one in the night, with reduced charges for the latter. The actual charging tariffs for these two time zones are determined by the electricity suppliers. These two time zones are determined by HEDNO and are different for the winter and summer season. More specifically, for the winter season: 1 November to 30 April 02:00-08:00 and 15:00-17:00 for customers connected to the Network of the Mainland and its interconnected islands and 02:00-08:00 and 15:30-17:30 for customers of non-interconnected islands and for the summer season: 1 May to 31 October 23:00-07:00. In addition, 'agricultural customers' have the chance to sign interruptible load contracts which is crucial for IPTO in order to maintain the integrity of the grid in periods of grid overloading.

⁴ [Data | IPTO \(admie.gr\)](https://www.admie.gr/)

Figure 4: Sample of the energy mix provided by the IPTO.

The liberalization of the Retail Market has created the need of a Social Household Tariff to protect the vulnerable groups of consumers. The discount granted to beneficiaries is common for all electricity suppliers. Several suppliers offer an add-on service which guarantees that the energy consumed within the household is equivalent to the amount generated and reserved from renewable energy, offering to the consumer a higher fixed price per kWh⁵. The same service is also provided to companies providing them with a Green Certificate⁶. The electricity supplied to the households is monitored by the RAE and cannot be priced dynamically through the day. However, dynamic pricing schemes can be deployed for the electricity sold through the EV charging stations. Moreover, bi-directional EV charging has not yet a legal frame in Greece, hence Vehicle to Grid or Vehicle to Home schemes cannot be yet deployed.

The Greek government is planning to offer significant incentives for the installation of rooftop PV panels by subsidising even the 60% of the whole cost⁷. The building-owners (prosumers) are eligible to consume in real-time the energy produced by their PV installation. If this energy is not sufficient for the energy needs of the household, then additional electricity is provided from the grid. On the other hand, if the produced energy exceeds the energy needs, the excess energy is fed back into the grid. This operation is known as the 'net-metering' scheme⁸. At the end of the month the produced electricity in kWh is deducted from the consumed kWh and the prosumer pays for the difference. If the produced electricity is constantly exceeding the consumed electricity, the electricity bill of the prosumer is zero at the end of each month and after some years, the prosumers will not be paying bills. Another service that is also provided by some Utilities in Greece such as Protergia, is the installation of a domestic battery along with the PV panels. The battery can be charged either during the day from the PV panels or directly from the grid. HEDNO has not predicted the overloads coming from the charge of multiple domestic batteries during the peak demand time because the market is still very small. However, shifting the direct charge from the grid of the domestic battery during the night will be mandatory the coming years. The energy stored in the battery can be used for the optimisation of the Demand-Response schemes or as a Backup in case of power failure. However, power trading among individuals is not authorised in Greece.

As for the regulatory framework around the Energy Communities, Greece has adopted the establishment and operation of the Energy Communities, as introduced and established by Law 4513/2018. Even though 176 energy communities have been established in Western Macedonia, an energy community facing important obstacles in order to smoothly operate. The administrative procedures are costly and complex, while the members of the

⁵ <https://www.dei.gr/en/home/electricity/greenpass/>

⁶ <https://www.protergia.gr/en/business/energy-solutions-services/the-green-certificate/>

⁷ <https://www.tornosnews.gr/en/tornos/green-travel/47748-greek-government-to-subsidise-rooftop-solar-panels-up-to-60-in-upcoming-program.html>

⁸ <https://www.c2h.gr/en/renewable-energy/net-metering>

community should be registered as tradesmen in the tax office. In addition, energy communities should compete with private investors in bids to ensure operational reinforcement for RES projects (Law 4414/2016)⁹.

2.3. Description of the Demonstration Plan

The timeframe of the different UCs which will be implemented in the settlement of Aspra Spitia is presented in Table 2. The responsible partners for the technical development of each UC are specified along with some comments regarding the work to be done before the trial period. Once the ACCEPT platform and all the relevant components are ready and fully integrated, the implementation of the UC will start. The end-users will be notified when the C-App is ready and live stream data from their houses are available.

Table 2: Timeframe for the implementation of the Use Cases in the Greek pilot site.

ID	UC Name	Responsible Partners	Expected starting time			
			M27	M28	M29	Comments
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data	QUE/ CERTH				Web and Mobile app will be able to live stream data from the houses
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation	HYPERTech/ QUE				The period of testing and the way of communicating the interventions to the end-users should be discussed
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting	HYPERTech/ QUE				Flexibility forecasting is the only module that should be developed
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation	WITSIDE/CIRCE	TBD			Data from the energy mix of each pilot country should be generated along with the wholesale market price
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility	QUE/ HYPERTech				The P2P flexibility tool will be simulated
UC8	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes	CERTH/HYPERTech/CIRCE/RINA				Need to agree how the user will receive notifications for the implementation of this scheme
UC9	Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes	CERTH/HYPERTech/CIRCE/RINA				It has been agreed that these DR signals will be deployed without initially notifying the end-users
UC11	Retailer day-ahead optimal pricing configuration	WITSIDE/ CIRCE	TBD			Same as UC4
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement	SIN/ UCC				Continuous evaluation through questionnaires and short interviews

3. Preparation of the Pilot Test-Bed

As a result of the activities described in T6.1, T6.5 and T6.6, the BoM and the deployment plan for each residential premise was created as described in D6.7. The installation of the smart equipment started in January 2023 and was completed at mid-February 2023. During these installations, the smart devices were linked to a central Raspberry Pi gateway. This gateway was commissioned to the ACCEPT server in collaboration with the technical team of Hypertech. Using the data collected from this gateway an analytical explanation of each UC which will be tested in the Aspra Spitia pilot premises is presented in Table 3.

⁹ [Executive summary: development of community energy in Greece under pressure - REScoop](#)

Table 3: Detailed description for the implementation of each UC in the Greek pilot site.

ID	UC Name	How UC is going to be tested
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data	Integration of the data from the smart devices to the BIML has been completed. The data will be visualised to the C-App and Community tool.
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation	The BIML will integrate data into the ACCEPT solution for the optimisation of the energy consumption in each house. In the Greek pilot site, there is no energy storage or production.
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting	The Building Digital Twin built for each residential premise will feed with input data the On-Demand Flexibility Manager. The goal is to forecast the demand at a consumer-level.
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation	The Demand Price Forecasting Tool has been built using real data from the Spanish energy mix. The model will be now trained with the real data from each pilot site and the energy price from the wholesale market in each pilot country to obtain the elasticity.
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility	This UC will be simulated as it is not possible due to current regulation and DSO limitations in each pilot country. This UC will investigate the benefits that can arise by optimising the demand-side at a community level.
UC8	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes	The model requests flexibility information at a consumer level to generate the optimal operational schedule of all the available controllable assets such as the AC units and the DHW.
UC9	Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes	A dynamic tariff scheme is needed for the implementation of this UC. Based on the variation of this network energy tariff throughout the day, the strategy for the implementation of flexibility (i.e., which devices and for how long), will be determined
UC11	Retailer day-ahead optimal pricing configuration	This is related to the UC4 and UC9. The goal is to create an optimal dynamic pricing scheme based on the demand elasticity data and the integrity of the grid.
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement	The goal of this UC is to build a strategic plan adapted to the particularities of each pilot site which will reassure the continuous engagement with the end-users and will identify the key issues for maintaining the interest of the participants.

4. Support activities

Maintaining the communication among the smart devices and the ACCEPT server is vital for the Demonstration Activities described in Table 3. For that purpose, a tool has been developed by Hypertech which allows the constant monitoring of the status of all the installed devices. The online monitoring tool gives an insight into the Connection Status of each device and allows the user to identify if the arising issues come from the gateway or the specific device. This identification makes it easier to understand if the device is faulty or if the resident made changes in his set-up without informing us. When an issue is observed the first level of support is activated. As a first step, the pilot manager is contacting the resident to inform him about the issue and to pose a series of key questions which will help him understand if the resident did something that interrupted the connection. If the devices have not been moved, Wi-fi connectivity issues should be investigated. It is often that the end-users change the credentials of their router without thinking about the smart device set-up. If the reason for the lost connectivity has not yet been identified, then the smart devices should be reset. If the issue persists, then the second level support should be put in place. The pilot manager in communication with Hypertech should explore together all the possible actions that can resolve the issue remotely. If the problem cannot be fixed remotely, a visit to the residential premises should be organized carrying along a new kit of the equipment. In the case that the issue remains unsolved, mitigation actions should be explored.

5. Next Steps

Most of the tests and the UCs will be ready in March 2023 (M27). The pilot managers and the demo partners will be able to observe the first implementations in M27 and the Demonstration Activities will continue until the M40. The status of the deployed devices will be continuously monitored and controlled through the monitoring tool and all the raised issues will be recorded in an Excel sheet.

Key modules for the initiation of the demo activities are the C-App and the Community App which will allow the end-users to visualize their data and control their devices. Having all the end-users engaged to the project and having the pilot manager in charge of the total consumption curves, all the above-mentioned UCs can be tested and the acceptance of the end-users can also be calculated. A more detailed description of these activities will be included in the second version of the Demonstration Activities report with all the collected results and the feedback from the end-users.

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